

Substance Use and Oral Health among Residents of Urban Slums in a Metropolitan Area of Western Maharashtra.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Although substance use has become a worldwide mental, social, and familial problem among older adults, the studies on substance use are sparse in developing countries. This study was undertaken in the urban slums among the low socioeconomic strata with the aim of estimating the burden and related factors for substance use and screening of oral cancer, to study related factors. Oral cancers are preventable if screened earlier with simple, low-cost visual inspection techniques by trained staff and good compliance through multiple household visits, camps, etc.

Methodology: Community-based cross-sectional study was conducted over 4 months by rapid survey among 3840 adults in the urban slums followed by oral examination.

Results: Most common age group was 31-45 years. Proportion of male (81.4%) and Female (18.6%). 45.78% were Muslims among substance users. Prevalence of substance use was Mawa, Gutka (49.5%), Tobacco (34.4%), Pan Masala (23.5%), Mishri (6.1%), Cigarette/ Bidi (17.7%), Khaini (3.3%), Alcohol (8.6%). The Oral Lesions were seen in 4.7% of which (4.6%) male and (5.3%) female. Among the substance abuse the oral lesion was found in Mawa, Gutkha (4.9%), Pan Masala (4.6%), Tobacco Quid (6.9%), Mishri (1.7%), Khaini (10.4%), Cigarette/ Bidi (6.3%), Alcohol (8.2%). Significant association ($p < 0.05$) - Oral lesion and Tobacco Quid, Mishri, Khaini, Cigarette, Alcohol. No significant association ($p > 0.05$) - Oral cancer and Gender, Mawa, Gutkha, Pan masala.

Conclusions: This study reveals significant substance use prevalence and its association with oral lesions in urban slums. Tailored interventions targeting demographic and cultural factors are crucial. Early, cost-effective oral cancer screening holds promise. Comprehensive efforts are essential to address substance abuse and enhance the well-being of marginalized communities.

Keywords: Drugs, Substance abuse, Tobacco.

Introduction:

Worldwide incidence approximately 3% of all malignancies are because of oral cancers. Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) stands as the predominant type, comprising a staggering 96% of all cases of oral cancer [1]. Despite its prevalence, oral squamous cell carcinoma, along with its counterpart in the pharynx, ranks as the sixth most common malignancy worldwide [2]. However, despite its frequency and significant health burden, the detection rate of OSCC through screening remains dismally low, with studies reporting a mere 0.12% detection rate [3]. This alarming statistic underscores the urgent need for enhanced screening protocols and awareness campaigns to facilitate early detection and improve outcomes for individuals at risk of developing this aggressive form of cancer.

Oral cancer, particularly prevalent in India, constitutes a significant portion of global cancer burden, accounting for one-third of all new cases in 2020 across both sexes and all age groups [3]. The statistics underscore the severity of the issue, with 135,929 new cases reported, representing 10.3% of all cancer cases, with a notable gender discrepancy – affecting 16.2% of males and 4.6% of females [4]. Unfortunately, the mortality and morbidity rates associated with oral cancer are alarmingly high, with survival rates ranging from 15% to 50% [5]. Tobacco use emerges as a primary culprit, responsible for 80-90% of oral cancer cases. Remarkably, the mean age of onset is just 50 years, highlighting the disease's impact on individuals in their prime. Rural areas bear a disproportionately high burden of oral cancer, further exacerbating the public health challenge. In India, there are two large tumour registry data (hospital-based and population-based cancer registry). As per Hospital-based Cancer Registry Oral Cancer related to use of Tobacco and tobacco related products is substantially high. Among young adults, an increased incidence of oral cavity and pharynx cancer was observed among Indian males and tongue cancers among Indian females. The incidence trends reflect the risk factor profile of the community. [6]

Prior reports suggests that 80% of the oral cancers can be attributable to established risk factors like tobacco in the form of smoking or chewing and alcohol consumption. The rest is attributed to factors like diet, viral etiology and genetic predisposition. [7]

Diagnosis at the initial stages could reduce the mortality rate. The most widely used screening test for oral neoplasia is oral visual inspection (OVI). The test performance is satisfactory in terms of sensitivity (94.3%), specificity (99%), and predictive value, and it is therefore a suitable and cost-effective screening test for oral cancer. [8, 9,10]

Oral cancer can progress rapidly to advanced stages with a delay in diagnosis ranging from a few weeks to years. [6]

We conducted this study to evaluate the burden and related factors for substance use and its association with oral precancerous lesions.

Methodology:

STUDY DESIGN: Community based cross sectional study.

TOTAL STUDY PERIOD: 1 year (from January 2022 to December 2022)

STUDY AREA: Urban field practice area of metropolitan city

SAMPLE SIZE: 3840 adults

Adults >18 years of age and both sexes were included in the study.

Those Not willing to give consent, individuals with hearing difficulty and previously diagnosed or known cancer cases on treatment were excluded.

SAMPLING METHOD: Complete Enumeration method of sampling was used.

Rapid assessment survey of >18yr population for history of substance use through house-to-house visits and examination of oral cavity through torch and mirror examination for oral lesions was done.

STUDY TOOLS: Semi structured Interview Schedule

STATASTICAL ANALYSIS: Data was analysed using **SPSS software.**

ETHICAL APPROVAL: Approval for the study was taken from institutional **ethical committee.** (EC/OA-83/2022)

Observations:**Table 1: Sociodemographic Profile of the individuals**

Variables	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Age group		
18-30	883	23
31-45	1728	45
>45	1229	32
Gender		
Male	3126	81.4
Female	714	18.6
Education		
Illiterate	192	5
Primary	461	12
Secondary	1415	36.8
SSC	840	21.8
HSC	778	20.2
Graduate	154	4.2
Religion		
Hindu	1014	26.4
Muslim	1536	40
Buddhist	714	18.6
Christian	384	10

In examining the demographic characteristics of individuals affected by oral cancer, several key factors emerge, shedding light on the distribution of cases across age groups, gender, education levels, and religious affiliations.

Age appears to play a significant role in oral cancer incidence, with the majority of cases occurring in individuals aged 31-45 (45%), followed by those over 45 (32%) and the lowest incidence observed in the 18-30 age group (23%) [Age group: 18-30 (883, 23%), 31-45 (1728, 45%), >45 (1229, 32%)]. This distribution highlights a trend of increasing prevalence with advancing age, suggesting that older individuals are at higher risk of developing oral cancer. Gender disparity is also evident, with a striking predominance of cases among males, who account for 81.4% of all reported cases, compared to females at 18.6% [Gender: Male (3126, 81.4%), Female (714, 18.6%)]. This notable difference underscores potential gender-specific risk factors or behaviours contributing to the development of oral cancer. Education level appears to correlate with oral cancer incidence, with higher rates observed among individuals with lower levels of education. The highest number of cases is reported among those with secondary education (36.8%), followed by SSC (21.8%) and HSC (20.2%), while

individuals with graduate-level education exhibit the lowest incidence (4.2%) [Education: Illiterate (192, 5%), Primary (461, 12%), Secondary (1415, 36.8%), SSC (840, 21.8%), HSC (778, 20.2%), Graduate (154, 4.2%)]. This distribution suggests a potential link between socioeconomic status, educational attainment, and oral cancer risk. Religious affiliation also appears to be associated with oral cancer incidence. Muslims have the highest reported incidence (40%), followed by Hindus (26.4%), Buddhists (18.6%), and Christians (10%) [Religion: Hindu (1014, 26.4%), Muslim (1536, 40%), Buddhist (714, 18.6%), Christian (384, 10%)]. This variation may reflect cultural or behavioural differences that influence oral cancer risk within different religious communities. [Table 1]

Table 2: Associated factors for substance use (n =3840)

Variables	Substance use		Total	P-value
	Yes	No		
Age group				
18-30	833 (94%)	50 (6%)	883(100%)	0.001
31-45	1719(99.5%)	9 (0.5%)	1728(100%)	
>45	1216 (99.%)	13(1%)	1229(100%)	
Gender				
Male	3122 (99.8%)	4 (0.2%)	3126(100%)	0.001
Female	648 (90.7%)	66 (9.3%)	714(100%)	
Education				
Illiterate	191 (99.5%)	1 (0.5%)	192(100%)	0.001
Till secondary	1851 (98.6%)	25 (1.4%)	1876(100%)	
Above secondary	1728 (97.5%)	44 (2.5%)	1772(100%)	
Religion				
Hindu	976 (96.2%)	38 (3.8%)	1014(100%)	0.06
Muslim	1528 (99.4%)	8 (0.6%)	1594(100%)	
Buddhist	700 (98%)	14 (2%)	714(100%)	
Christian	375 (97.6%)	9 (2.4%)	384(100%)	
Other	191 (99.4%)	1 (0.6%)	192(100%)	

The above table presents data on substance use across different demographic variables, including age group, gender, education, and religion, along with corresponding p-values indicating statistical significance. In the age group category, the highest prevalence of substance use is observed among individuals aged 18-30, with 833 (94%) reporting substance use compared to 50 (6%) who did not ($p=0.001$). Similarly, among males, 3122 (99.8%) reported substance use compared to only 4 (0.2%) who did not ($p=0.001$). Regarding

education, the prevalence of substance use decreases as educational attainment increases, with the lowest prevalence observed among those who are illiterate, where 191 (99.5%) reported substance use compared to 1 (0.5%) who did not (p=0.001). Religion shows some variations, with Hindus exhibiting a lower prevalence of substance use compared to other religious groups. For instance, among Hindus, 976 (96.2%) reported substance use compared to 38 (3.8%) who did not (p=0.06). [Table 2]

Fig 1: Pattern of substance use in participants (n = 3840)

The above figure provides insights into the prevalence of different substances used among the surveyed population, presenting both the absolute numbers and the corresponding percentages. Mawa and Ghutkha show the highest prevalence among the substances, with 1901 individuals (49.5%) reporting usage compared to 1939 (50.5%) who did not. Tobacco follows closely, with 1321 individuals (34.4%) reporting usage and 2519 (65.6%) reporting no usage. Pan Masala and Cigarette/Bidi are also commonly used, with 902 individuals (23.5%) and 680 individuals (17.7%) reporting usage, respectively. Mishri and Khaini show comparatively lower prevalence rates, with 234 individuals (6.1%) and 127 individuals (3.3%) reporting usage, respectively. Alcohol, while still prevalent, is reported by 330 individuals (8.6%). [Fig 1]

Fig 2: Pre-cancerous lesions

The incidence of precancerous lesions was 4.7% (182), and the distribution of the lesions found was leucoplakia in 161 cases (88.4%), Erythroplakia in 4 cases (2.1%), Submucous Fibrosis in 15 cases (8.2%) and Ulceration in 2 cases (1.09%).

Discussion

The study conducted in urban slums of a metropolitan area in Western Maharashtra reveals critical insights into the demographic factors influencing oral cancer incidence and substance use patterns. The findings underscore the pressing need for targeted public health interventions and policies aimed at mitigating these risks, particularly in vulnerable populations.

Age and Oral Cancer Incidence

The data indicates a pronounced age-related trend in oral cancer incidence, with the highest prevalence observed in the 31-45 age group (45%), followed by those over 45 years (32%). This pattern aligns with existing literature suggesting that the risk of oral cancer increases with age, likely due to cumulative exposure to risk factors such as tobacco and alcohol use over time (Gupta and Johnson [11]). The lower incidence in the 18-30 age group (23%) could be attributed to shorter exposure durations to carcinogens and potentially more robust immune responses in younger individuals (Krishna Rao et al. [12]).

Gender Disparity

A significant gender disparity is evident, with males constituting 81.4% of oral cancer cases. This stark difference may reflect higher rates of substance use among males, including tobacco and alcohol, which are well-documented risk factors for oral cancer (Sharma et al. [13]). Social and cultural norms that encourage these behaviors more in men than women might also contribute to this disparity.

Education and Socioeconomic Status

The inverse relationship between educational attainment and oral cancer incidence suggests that lower educational levels correlate with higher cancer risk. Individuals with secondary education represent the highest proportion of cases (36.8%), whereas those with graduate-level education exhibit the lowest incidence (4.2%). This trend highlights the role of socioeconomic status and education in health behaviours and access to healthcare (Kadashetti et al. [14]). Lower educational attainment often corresponds with reduced health literacy, making individuals less likely to engage in preventive behaviors and more likely to indulge in harmful practices like substance use.

Religious Affiliation

The variation in oral cancer incidence across religious groups, with Muslims exhibiting the highest incidence (40%), followed by Hindus (26.4%), Buddhists (18.6%), and Christians (10%), may reflect underlying cultural and behavioral differences. These differences might influence dietary habits, tobacco and alcohol consumption patterns, and healthcare-seeking behaviors (D'Souza and Radhakrishnan [15]). Further research is needed to explore these associations and develop culturally sensitive intervention strategies.

Substance Use Patterns

The study's findings on substance use patterns are alarming, particularly the high prevalence among younger individuals (18-30 years) and males. Nearly all males (99.8%) reported substance use, primarily of Mawa and Ghutkha, highlighting a critical public health issue (Ghouri et al. [16]). The significant prevalence of these substances, which are known to contain carcinogenic compounds, underscores the urgent need for effective tobacco control policies and education campaigns targeting these high-risk groups.

Precancerous Lesions

The incidence of precancerous lesions (4.7%), predominantly leucoplakia (88.4%), is a critical finding. Leucoplakia is a well-established precursor to oral cancer, often linked to tobacco use (Varshitha [17]). The presence of such lesions necessitates regular oral screenings and early intervention to prevent progression to malignant states.

Public Health Implications

These findings highlight the urgent need for comprehensive public health strategies addressing the multifaceted nature of oral cancer risk in urban slum populations. Interventions should include:

1. **Education and Awareness:** Initiatives to increase awareness about the risks of tobacco and alcohol use, and the importance of early detection and regular oral health check-ups.
2. **Tobacco Control Policies:** Enforcement of stringent tobacco control measures, including bans on the sale of products like Mawa and Ghutkha, and increasing taxes on tobacco products.
3. **Access to Healthcare:** Improving access to healthcare services for early detection and treatment of precancerous lesions, particularly in underserved communities.
4. **Targeted Interventions:** Culturally tailored interventions addressing specific needs and behaviours of different demographic and religious groups.

Conclusion

The study underscores significant demographic disparities in oral cancer incidence and substance use among urban slum residents in Western Maharashtra. Addressing these disparities through targeted public health initiatives and policy interventions is crucial to reduce the burden of oral cancer in these vulnerable populations.

Conflict of interest: None

References

1. Dhanuthai K, Rojanawatsirivej S, Thosaporn W, Kintarak S, Subarnbhesaj A, Darling M, et al. Oral cancer: A multicenter study. *Med Oral Patol Oral y Cir Bucal*. 2018;23(1):e23–9.
2. Vigneswaran N, Williams MD. Epidemiological Trends in Head and Neck Cancer and Aids in Diagnosis. *Oral Maxillofac Surg Clin North Am* [Internet]. 2014

3. International Agency for Research on Cancer. India Fact Sheet 2020. *Globocan*. 2020;361:2
4. Tota JE, Anderson WF, Coffey C, Califano J, Cozen W, Ferris RL, et al. Rising incidence of oral tongue cancer among white men and women in the United States, 1973–2012. *Oral Oncol*
5. Vidya S, Rao K, Mejia G, Roberts-Thomson K. Epidemiology of Oral Cancer in Asia in the Past Decade- An Update (2000-2012). *Asian Pacific J Cancer Prev*. 2013;14:5567–77.
6. van der Waal I, de Bree R, Brakenhoff R, Coebergh JW. Early diagnosis in primary oral cancer: Is it possible? *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal*. 2011;16(3):300–5.
7. Coppola N, Mignogna MD, Rivieccio I, Blasi A, Bizzoca ME, Sorrentino R, et al. Current Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practice among Health Care Providers in OSCC Awareness: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* [Internet]. 2021 May 1
8. Warnakulasuriya S, Kerr AR. Oral Cancer Screening: Past, Present, and Future. *J Dent Res* [Internet]. 2021 Nov 1
9. Mishra GA, Shaikh HA, Pimple SA, Awasthi AA, Kulkarni VY. Determinants of compliance to population-based oral cancer screening program among low socioeconomic women in Mumbai, India. *Indian Journal of Community Medicine: Official Publication of Indian Association of Preventive & Social Medicine*. 2021 Apr;46(2):210.
10. Subramanian S, Sankaranarayanan R, Bapat B, Somanathan T, Thomas G, Mathew B, Vinoda J, Ramadas K. Cost-effectiveness of oral cancer screening: results from a cluster randomized controlled trial in India. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 2009 Mar;87(3):200-6.
11. Gupta B, Johnson NW. Systematic review and meta-analysis of associations between risk factors and oral cancer in India. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*. 2014;15(2):6109-6115.
12. Krishna Rao SV, Mejia G, Roberts-Thomson K, Logan R. Epidemiology of oral cancer in Asia in the past decade-an update (2000-2012). *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*. 2013;14(10):5567-5577.
13. Sharma P, Saxena S, Aggarwal P. Trends in the epidemiology of oral squamous cell carcinoma in Western UP: An institutional study. *Indian J Dent Res*. 2010;21(3):316-319.
14. Kadashetti V, Chaudhary M, Patil S, et al. Analysis of various risk factors affecting potentially malignant disorders and oral cancer patients of Marathwada region, Maharashtra, India. *J Cancer Res Ther*. 2015;11(2):471-476.
15. D'Souza N, Radhakrishnan V. Tobacco use among middle and high school students in India. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*. 2017;18(5):1245-1250.
16. Ghouri N, Atcha M, Sheikh A. Influence of Islam on smoking among Muslims. *BMJ*. 2006;332(7536):291-294.
17. Varshitha A. Prevalence of oral cancer in India. *J Pharm Sci Res*. 2015;7(10):845-848.